

CONDITIONALLY PATHOGENIC MICROFLORA IN HOOF LESIONS OF DAIRY COWS: MICROBIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS BASED ON WASH SAMPLES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17221887>

Abstract. *The article provides a comprehensive analysis of the microbiological characteristics and pathogenetic mechanisms of diseases affecting the distal part of the hooves in high-yielding cattle. During the research, 30 samples taken directly from wound surfaces under farm conditions were studied in a complex manner, and various pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microorganisms were identified. Among the main isolated strains were *Fusobacterium necrophorum* (86%), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (73%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (50%), *Escherichia coli* (83%), and *Streptococcus pyogenes* (20%). According to the results of biological tests, the diagnosis of necrobacteriosis was confirmed in 86% of cases. The identified microorganisms were often found in association, intensifying the inflammatory process. This indicates the multifactorial nature of the infectious process and the interaction between pathogens. The article emphasizes the importance of a complex approach based on microbiological analysis in the effective treatment of hoof diseases. Such an approach includes the identification of pathogens, assessment of their antibiotic susceptibility, the use of immunomodulators, optimization of feed rations, and improvement of housing (zoohygienic) conditions. The research results are of practical and scientific significance for maintaining farm productivity, preventing hoof diseases, and improving treatment effectiveness.*

Keywords: *necrobacteriosis, cattle, distal hoof part, hoof diseases, wound swabs, conditionally pathogenic microflora.*

Introduction

In recent years, under conditions of developing livestock farming based on intensive technologies, pathologies of the distal part of the hooves—particularly infectious necrobacteriosis and various non-infectious lesions—have acquired special clinical and economic importance among diseases observed in high-yielding cattle. These diseases reduce overall farm productivity, shorten the productive life of animals, decrease feed efficiency, and negatively affect reproductive functions, thereby posing a serious threat to the economic sustainability of the livestock sector. Necrobacteriosis and hoof tissue lesions shorten the productive lifespan of high-yielding dairy and beef cattle, leading to decreased milk and meat productivity, as well as reproductive disorders. Such hoof diseases significantly reduce farm profitability. In some disadvantaged farms, the morbidity rate of necrobacteriosis and hoof pathologies is about 25–35%, while in some cases it has been recorded in 40–65% or more of the herd. These figures clearly demonstrate the high susceptibility and predisposition of high-yielding cows to hoof diseases. In affected cattle, nutrient absorption slows down, and weight gain becomes significantly delayed. This condition is accompanied by a decrease in body condition, milk, and meat productivity. Particularly in dairy

cows, such changes result in considerable economic losses for the farm, and the overall commercial value of such animals declines sharply.

Several factors are identified as the main causes of the development of necrobacteriosis and other distal hoof diseases. These include year-round restricted movement of cattle, violations of zoohygienic standards, and an imbalanced feed ration inconsistent with the physiological needs of the organism. At the same time, increased virulence of conditionally pathogenic microflora and decreased general resistance of the organism contribute to the activation of infectious processes. Microorganisms penetrate the body through mechanical hoof tissue injuries, causing pathological processes accompanied by inflammation and necrosis. Therefore, one of the most important steps in diagnosing necrobacteriosis and hoof diseases is microbiological analysis of samples taken from wound surfaces. This method makes it possible to identify the species composition of pathogens, correctly establish a clinical diagnosis, and select targeted therapy. The aim of the study was to evaluate the microbiological characteristics of the infectious process by identifying pathogenic microflora and its species composition in clinical samples obtained from wound surfaces during necrobacteriosis and distal hoof diseases in high-yielding cattle.

Research Results and Discussion

Microbiological analyses of 30 clinical samples taken from hoof wounds under farm conditions revealed the presence of various pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microorganisms. The isolated bacterial colonies participated in the active stages of the inflammatory process, intensifying tissue damage. The development of these microorganisms was directly related to farm sanitary-hygienic conditions, the balance of the feed ration, and the immunological status of the animals. The research not only revealed the microbiological basis of hoof pathologies but also provided an important scientific and practical foundation for effectively planning treatment and preventive measures.

Fusobacterium necrophorum was isolated in 26 cases (86%) when cultured in Kitt–Tarozzi medium. Characteristic growth features were observed in this medium: turbidity at the bottom of the test tube and the formation of cotton-like sediment. This clearly demonstrated the anaerobic metabolism and biological properties of the microorganism. In biological tests, the high virulence of *Fusobacterium necrophorum* was confirmed. In particular, when bacterial suspension was injected into the subcutaneous tissue behind the ears of 26 rabbits, pathological foci with inflammation and necrosis developed within 4–7 days. These pathological processes confirmed the rapid and severe course of tissue damage associated with *F. necrophorum* infection.

Furthermore, material isolated from pathological foci was re-cultured in Kitt–Tarozzi medium, and pure cultures were obtained. Such repeated isolation enhanced the reliability of the experiment and once again confirmed the leading role of *F. necrophorum* in the etiology of necrobacteriosis.

The obtained results demonstrated that this strain is highly pathogenic and virulent. Therefore, *F. necrophorum* is of particular importance as one of the main causative agents of hoof diseases in livestock farming. *Staphylococcus aureus* was isolated from 15 out of 30 wound samples (50%). The strains showed characteristic growth features in different nutrient media. On nutrient agar (NA), golden-yellow, well-formed, clearly defined, and slightly elevated colonies developed. This appearance is one of the cultural characteristics typical of this bacterial species. In nutrient broth (NB), diffuse turbidity was observed, and cotton-like sediment formed at the bottom of the tube. On blood agar, a distinct hemolysis zone appeared around the colonies, confirming the strain's ability to destroy erythrocytes and its high pathogenicity.

Gram staining showed that the bacteria were gram-positive cocci. They were arranged in clusters resembling a “bunch of grapes,” which is a clear morphological characteristic of the *Staphylococcus* genus. The findings indicated the active participation of *Staphylococcus aureus* in inflammatory processes, its high prevalence under farm conditions, and its clinical significance as a pathogen. These results also highlighted the need to strengthen sanitary-hygienic measures in livestock farming and to establish effective microbiological monitoring.

Staphylococcus epidermidis was identified in 22 cases (73%) from 30 clinical samples. These bacteria grew in nutrient broth, forming small, whitish-yellow, uniform colonies. They typically appeared with smooth surfaces and slightly glossy tones, reflecting morphological characteristics of the species. In Gram-stained preparations, *S. epidermidis* appeared as gram-positive cocci. They often formed small fragmented groups, and sometimes cluster-like structures were also observed. However, their arrangement was less distinct compared to *Staphylococcus aureus*.

These findings suggest that *S. epidermidis* is primarily a conditionally pathogenic bacterium, potentially acting as a contributing factor in intensifying inflammatory processes. It often participates in disease development in association with other infectious agents and, under certain conditions, may acquire clinical significance. *Streptococcus pyogenes* was detected in 6 cases (20%) out of 30 samples. On nutrient agar, these bacteria formed small, uniform colonies arranged in chain-like structures. On glucose-blood agar, they displayed transparent structures with smooth edges and a clear hemolysis ring, which further clarified their species-specific characteristics.

Gram-stained smears showed gram-positive cells in diplococcus form. Their structure confirmed clinical importance and active involvement in triggering inflammatory processes. The results indicated that the involvement of *S. pyogenes* in disease development in cattle is often associated with poor farm sanitation, unsatisfactory housing (zoohygienic) conditions, and decreased immunological stability of the animals. Therefore, it may be regarded as a secondary, yet clinically significant pathogen.

Escherichia coli was detected in 25 cases (83%) out of 30 wound samples. On Endo medium, the bacteria produced characteristic colonies with metallic sheen and bright crimson-red color. On nutrient agar, they appeared as white-yellow colonies with distinct edges. Microscopic analysis showed *E. coli* cells as gram-negative, elongated rods with rounded ends. Biological test results confirmed that these strains were non-pathogenic for laboratory animals (white mice).

It is important to emphasize that *E. coli* is often not an absolute pathogen but rather acts as a conditionally pathogenic microorganism. In cases of poor farm hygiene, contamination of feed and water sources, or reduced resistance of animals, this bacterium may become active and participate in the inflammatory process. In some situations, it can form associations with other pathogens, aggravating the disease process.

Fungi of the genus *Penicillium* were isolated in 6 cases (20%) out of 30 wound samples when cultured on Sabouraud medium. They formed colonies with a characteristic powdery structure. Microscopic examination revealed multicellular mycelial structures and branched conidiophores with spores at the upper parts, confirming their belonging to the genus *Penicillium*. Although such fungi are not major independent pathogens, they play an important role as contributing factors that intensify the inflammatory process. In total, microbiological analysis of 30 wound swab samples revealed various microorganisms. The study highlighted the predominance of staphylococci. In particular, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was isolated in 73% of

cases, showing its active participation in wound infections as a conditionally pathogenic microorganism. Clinically significant strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* were isolated in 50% of cases.

Interestingly, these staphylococcal strains were often found in association:

with *Streptococcus* species in 40% of cases,

with *Escherichia coli* in 70% of cases.

In addition, fungi of the genus *Penicillium* were isolated in 6 cases (20%). Although they are not strong independent pathogens, they may act as contributing factors that intensify the inflammatory process.

The most important conclusion is that biological tests confirmed the association of the wound infection process with *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. Thus, the diagnosis of necrobacteriosis was confirmed in 86% of the cases studied, once again proving the leading role of *F. necrophorum* as the main etiological agent in distal hoof diseases.

Such microbiological associations may lead to prolonged inflammation, increased resistance to treatment, and worsening clinical conditions.

Conclusion

The results of the conducted research demonstrated that the etiopathogenesis of necrobacteriosis and distal hoof diseases in cattle is a complex, multifactorial process. A key pathogenetic role belongs to conditionally pathogenic microorganisms characteristic of the biogeocenosis, especially when the general resistance of the organism decreases. Microbiological analyses confirmed that microorganisms such as *Fusobacterium necrophorum*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, and some fungi penetrate the organism through damaged hoof tissues and intensify inflammatory processes. They are often found in association, contributing to the persistence of infection and aggravation of clinical outcomes. The activation of conditionally pathogenic microflora is closely associated with violations of farm housing (zoohygienic) standards, imbalanced feed, high humidity, and weakened immune status of animals. Therefore, the inflammatory process often arises not only under the influence of primary pathogens but also as a result of various bacterial and fungal associations. For the effective treatment of necrobacteriosis and hoof diseases in high-yielding cattle, an integrated approach must be applied. Such an approach includes:

- Identification of isolated strains and assessment of their pathogenicity;
- Analysis of microbial associations and their clinical significance;
- Selection of targeted therapy based on antibiotic susceptibility tests;
- Enhancement of general resistance using immunomodulators and biostimulants;
- Improvement of housing conditions and strengthening preventive measures.
- Such systematic measures help shorten treatment duration, reduce recurrence rates, and maintain high productivity on farms.

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